

**Consent Without Voice: Subaltern Silence and the Punished Subject in Franz Kafka's
*In the Penal Colony***

Afifa Munawar	BS English Literature, Department of English, University of Narowal. Email: afifamunawar00@gmail.com
Khadija Kousar	BS English Literature, Department of English, University of Narowal. Email: khadijakousar669@gmail.com
Sehrish Kabeer	BS English Literature, Department of English, University of Narowal. Email: shariikabeer@gmail.com
Tooba Chaudhry	BS English Literature, Department of English, University of Narowal. Email: toobachaudhry54@gmail.com

Abstract: *This study analyzes Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* through Spivak's lens to explore the representation of consent without voice through the silenced punished body. While existing scholarship has largely interpreted the story as a universal relevance of bureaucracy and authoritarian regimes. The aim of this study is to explore what the mechanisms of silenced consent mean within the narrative of *In the Penal Colony* and their significance with regard to colonial justice. This study will be guided with readings through Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's "Subaltern" with her work in "Can the Subaltern Speak?", with a qualitative methodology through a narrative textual analysis led with a focus on narrative mechanisms and symbolic representation through the narrative mechanisms such as the execution machine. This study will show how the punished man's obedience lacks any actual form of voice through a system where neither knowledge of law, nor the ability to speak, nor action, is granted. Furthermore, the execution machine serves as a representation of "epistemic violence" which replaces speech with inscription through the body and where justice becomes a form of domination. In highlighting the elements of silence, representation, and asymmetrical power relations in the text, this reading re-values *In the Penal Colony* as a text that critiques colonialist notions of justice and the ideological impossibility of subaltern discourse.*

Keywords: Colonial Justice, Consent without Voice, Epistemic Violence, Subalternity, Silence

Introduction

Franz Kafka was a Jewish Czech writer and novelist who wrote in German. He was born in Prague in the Austro-Hungarian Empire. He is considered one of the greatest writers of the 20th century. His works combined elements of realism and fantastique and were often characterized by a sense of isolated protagonists who face strange or surreal situations and unintelligible socio-bureaucratic forces. The word 'Kafkaesque' has gone on to enter the language in order to define situations such as those in his works. His famous works include the novella *The Metamorphosis* (1915) and the novels *The Trial* (1924) and *The Castle* (1926). He is also celebrated for his brief fables and aphorisms, which often included comedic features side-by-side with the more ominous themes found in his full-length writings. His writings have been an influence on artists, philosophers, musicians, movie-makers, literary

historians, religious scholars, and cultural theorists, and have been deemed to be prophetic of a totalitarian future.

One of Kafka's highly significant work is *In the Penal Colony* (1919), which is the focus of this study. In this short story, Kafka presents a brutal execution device in a remote penal colony, where justice is only associated with machine and the punishment becomes both ritualistic and dehumanizing. Kafka interrogates the interplay between authority, consent and human agency through vivid imagery and unsettling narrative techniques. This work provides fertile ground for exploring themes of subalternity, silence, and coercion as it portrays characters subjected to punishment without meaningful participation in their own fate. The context of the *In the Penal Colony* echo beyond its early twentieth century setting. However, the themes it portrays are universal in nature. Through a lens of subalternity, it is possible to position "*In the Penal Colony*" in relation to those communities which are oppressed and do not get a hearing in society in spite of their suffering at the hands of oppression. Although Kafka's story is set in a fictional colony, it provides conceptual parallels to "internal colonies" within modern nations, where marginalized groups experience social, legal, or economic subjugation. This study foregrounds questions of consent, silence, and the construction of punished subjects.

The purpose of this research is to explore the mechanism of consent and silence represented in *In the Penal Colony*, highlighting how the text represents the experience of subaltern in relation to power and punishment in Kafka's work. This research aims to identify the dynamics of power as they exist in the text, in which power is exerted explicitly and implicitly in matters of consent. The significance of this study is that it proposes an original reading of Kafka as it reveals the points of intersection of subaltern theory, colonial dynamics and ethics of punishment, which have been considered relatively underexplored areas in literary criticism. While linking it to broader socio-political concerns, including the structures of marginalization in contemporary societies, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of Kafka's work. In short, the current work places the penal colony of Kafka in relation to that of today's modern internal colonies. This analysis is guided by the central research question, "How does Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* represent consent without voice through the silence of the punished subject?"

Literature Review:

The Officer's canonical devotion to the machine reveals the peril of an indiscriminate commitment to the law as it systematically privileges order over humanity. This ambivalence is celebrated in the contradictions of the story by Steinberg (1976) as an encouragement to critical debate rather than consensus. His discussion centers upon the conflict between the absolute faith in the law and the responsibilities of morality as illustrated most forcibly in the distinction between the Old and New Commandants. In this article, digital rule is presented as an emerging form of power made possible by electronic forms of monitoring that operate across time and space. Building on Foucault's concept of disciplinary power, this article contends that modern justice system has been gradually adopting indirect and at-a-distance control rather than bodily discipline. From the idea of control societies described in Deleuze's notion of control societies, the study shows how digital technology changes control in decision making and punishment. Surveillance boundaries between punishment and control become less defined. This framework is important for understanding contemporary punishment in technologically enabled governance (O'Malley, 2009).

Anat Danziger (2011) presents a distinctive reading of Franz Kafka's "*In the Penal Colony*" by identifying the punishment apparatus as a "vibrating human machine", for the production of fear, not punishment. In this context, departing from traditional allegorical interpretations that emphasizes the

bureaucratic terror, suggesting instead that fear is produced through the interiorization of violence in the human body. However, the uncanny environment produced in Kafka's narrative allows for the production of knowledge that is reduced to confusion is followed by blindness (Danziger, 2011). Ruth Cumberland (2013) interprets Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* as a potent warning against systems of governance founded upon absolute power, control, and dehumanization. She places the text within the discourses of colonialism and post colonialism; she aligns the penal system in Kafka with those historical practices of domination of colonies. With the help of scholars like John Zilcosky, Cumberland relates the story to German colonialism and to later imperial contexts such as postcolonial India and Iraq. She stresses how the character called the Condemned Man is racialized into the position of the colonial "Other," the site on which power, punishment, and exclusion are violently inscribed.

Scholarly interpretation of *In the Penal Colony* focus on the ways in which the power of sovereignty writes itself directly upon the human body. The nature of the execution machine is to inscribe the body as a text upon which power and law are the same thing supporting the ideology of the power of discipline evident within the works of Michel Foucault (Foucault, 1977; Brickabraak, 2017). In Kafka's narrative, the condemned man receives his sentence through the agony of his physical body, describing the power that does not require dialogue or defense and transforms the human body into a medium of power and sovereign knowledge. This article critically examines the ethics of live ethnography as an evidenced by the problematic role of the ethnographer as a Condoner of power through an interpretive engagement with Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony*. In research carried out by live ethnography across prisons in Uganda, India and Myanmar, the study conceptualizes ethnography to implicate all researchers as an inadvertent accomplice to bureaucratic violence. "Edifying qualms" distinguishes experiencing ethics as simultaneously analytical and problematic, revealing how bureaucratic regimes normalize harm while obscuring human agency (Martin, 2019). Pierce's work presents a postcolonial and critical race interpretation of Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* resisting the tendency to see text as a universal allegory of power. The emphasis here is on the penal colony as a specifically colonial space and the role of race in structuring power in the text. Pierce's interpretation relies on a range of theorist such as Franz Fanon, Achille Mbembe, and Saidiya Hartman and presents an interpretation of the work by Kafka as one that engages specifically with mechanism of colonial power and racialized violence through the power of law and punishment (Pierce, 2020). One of the Kafka's most celebrated text, *In the Penal Colony* has been widely interpreted as a critique of justice and violence authorized by authoritarian regimes. Recent interpretation emphasizes the symbolic meaning of the execution machine as a tool or ideology through which power inscribes ideology onto the human body, turning the latter into a mere object of the state. Urbaite argues that Kafka reveals the blindness of the authoritative regime when it portrays obedience as complicity and law as a ritual rather than a moral practice. The fanaticism of the officer, who is devoted to the precepts of the law, and the subsequent breakdown of the machine underscore the instability of the violence (Urbaite, 2025).

Existing scholarship on Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* has until now been concerned with themes of authoritarianism, mechanical justice and general structural models of power, often through Foucauldian or essential frameworks. While these readings are well utilized, essentially they originate in a kind of universalized approach to oppression and overlook the colonial context as one of the particular historical and political simplicity. There is a notable lack of sustained analysis in the literature for a detailed discussion of the structurally relevant aspects of the colonial relations of power and the silenced voice of the "Other", the condemned man, through a postcolonial lens that interrogates representation and epistemic violence. This gap is important in view of the fact ignoring the colonial context might lead to a de-politicization of Kafka's criticism, where it might become difficult to understand how system of justice operate differently on marginalized bodies. In this regard, Spivak's theory is utilized, specifically with regards to her idea of subalterns to examine how colonial justice systematically erases voice, agency, and representation. The punished man is often approached metaphorically, not as a racialized or colonized body affected by epistemic violence. The application

of the theory of Spivak is essential, as it enables this investigation to determine not merely whether the subaltern voice in Kafka's text can "speak" but also the manner in which the justice system functions as a means of actively precluding the possibility of the subaltern being heard. Spivak's framework enables a discussion on how the condemned man is deprived of speech, deed, and subjectivity, to uncover how colonial power makes subalterns incapable of being heard within dominant discourse of law and justice.

Research Methodology:

This study adopts a qualitative, interpretive approach to textual analysis as its primary research method. Qualitative literary analysis is particularly most suitable in the analysis of meaning, silence, and power relations in purely literary texts, as it permits a close reading of the text in relation to language, narratives, and character. Since the proposed research aims to interpret colonial justice, silence, and subalternity in Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony*, a non-empirical or theory guided approach becomes most suitable. The proposed research has a qualitative approach as it does not depend on data in the form of the figures.

The method used is close reading, the study highlights key scenes in the narrative, narrative voices, character placement, and symbolic elements in the form of execution machine, Officer, Explorer, and the condemned man. The moment of silence, non-consent and the absence of legal terms in the narrative are strategies employed in the narrative and have implications in terms of the representation of the colonial power. Secondary sources, including critical essays and peer reviewed journal articles, in an attempt to contextualize existing scholarship and locate a lacuna in interpretations, but the primary emphasis remains on the literary text itself.

The theoretical framework for this study is postcolonial theory, specifically the idea of the subaltern as expounded by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, Spivak's ideas are best articulated in her seminal text, "Can the subaltern speak?" (1988), where she argues that 'the subaltern cannot speak' does not mean that the subaltern cannot speak, but that the subaltern's speech, even if it were possible, would not be heeded. The word 'cannot' in the phrase 'the subaltern cannot speak' indicates power, not inability. Moreover, the phrase does not refer to the voice, but to its interpretation.

By combining qualitative textual analysis with Spivak's post-colonial theory, this methodology consequently provides nuanced insight into how Kafka criticized colonial justice. Such an approach has helped to bring out the elements in literature whereby colonial power operates on both the body and voice of the oppressed. This is an appropriate methodological approach because it foregrounds issues such as silencing, representation, and power that are central concerns of both the research topic and Spivak's theoretical intervention.

Analysis:

Despite the extensive analysis of Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* in terms of bureaucracy, authoritarians, technology, and abstract power system, a research gap emerged within existing literature. A predominantly critical analysis has generalized the text as a general allegory of oppression, and in

doing so, has ignored the existence of the penal colony as a site of colonialism and neglecting how race, colonial difference, and epistemic violence play out in relation to the text. Furthermore, though postcolonial analysis has occurred in relation to the text, few studies employ Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's theory of the subaltern in a sustained and theoretically robust manner. This gap is particularly striking given that Kafka's text dramatizes the phenomenon which Spivak's work describes. By applying the ideas of subalternity, epistemic violence, and representation as conceived in the works of the Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, this analysis seeks to re-evaluate the significance of *In the Penal Colony* in the context of subaltern speech within colonial systems of justice. In her influential essay, "Can the Subaltern Speak?", Spivak convincingly tackles the theme that the subalterns, or the socially excluded from political and epistemic representation, cannot occupy the position of the speaker within the mainstream discourse. As Spivak asserts, "the subaltern cannot speak" (Spivak, 1988), meaning that subaltern is neither speechless nor chosen to be so but always rendered speechless or silenced through the hegemonic discourse. In Kafka's narrative, the sentenced man represents the subaltern condition. For instance, he is never informed of his crime, not given the possibility to defend himself or to speak through the language system. The sentenced man is actually speechless on purpose through the judicial system he is subjected to. This adds up to Spivak's definition of the subaltern condition and covers the theoretical deficiency found within the interpretation of the sentenced man as the vicarious victim instead of the colonized other.

The penal colony itself is also a manifestation of the power of the colonizers in space. It is detached from the rest of the empire and is governed by an independent body of laws with the force of unquestionable will. This corresponds with the views of Spivak on how the empire exercises power over the colony through an experimental space that is often under the pretext of order restoration. When the Officer persists in the use of the execution machine, for example, he embodies the views of Spivak as the colonized people internalize the imperial ideology. His confidence in the system comes from the fact that the convicted do not understand the system he adheres to. According to Spivak: "imperialism's epistemic violence lies in the construction of the colonial subject as Other" (Spivak, 1988). Through the text by Kafka, the convicted is made a passive object for punishment rather than a subject of the law because he is subaltern. At the heart of this analysis is the idea of epistemic violence, described by Spivak as the destruction or erasure of native forms of knowledge by colonialist epistemologies. The execution machine, from *In the Penal Colony*, materializes epistemic violence as it reduces the law to a bodily inscription on the convicted person. The law is not started, it is inscribed. This horrific moment exemplifies that colonialist justice is one that is not based on dialogue or reason but, rather, force and control of the body. Spivak states that the violence of imperialist epistemic, social, and disciplinary inscription makes the speech of the subaltern unintelligible. Kafka's machine is a perfect illustration of this violence as it reduces the convicted man's body to a text inscribed by the colonialist.

This mechanization of justice also puts Enlightenment ideals of reason and progress under pressure. The Officer's presentation of the machine as a rational and efficient device serves in contrast to the very uncanny purpose it satisfies. Spivak's critique of Western humanism shows itself relevant in this regard. Spivak indicates how Enlightenment reason itself tends to cover over imperial domination, speaking always in the name of universality but simultaneously erasing subaltern subjects. The word "justice" itself falls apart under examination, revealing instead a system of self-perpetuating terror and silence. It is in these respects, of course, that Kafka anticipates Spivak's argument about the complicity of modern legal and philosophical discourse in the erasure of subaltern subjects. The figure of the Explorer adds more to the research gap that this analysis aims to fill. Regularly viewed from the perspective of a moral witness or a humanitarian stranger, the Explorer might better be seen in the terms of Spivak's criticism of Western intellectuals' efforts to speak for the subaltern. Spivak has argued that "the intellectual is complicit in the persistent constitution of the Other as the self's shadow" (Spivak, 1988). Despite listening to the Officer's explanation and voicing his discomfort, the Explorer does not take a catalyzing step. His silence and eventual departure reveal the failure of a humanist approach to

intervention. He does not allow the condemned to speak for himself, and he becomes the next mediator who observes and does not disturb the social mechanism. This observation is a part of the research gap in Kafka studies that has insufficiently accused the Explorer for his failure to allow the subaltern to speak. Representation is an important issue in Spivak's theory that has a direct link to Kafka's narrative technique. Spivak makes a clear distinction between representation (Vertretung) and re-presentation (Darstellung) and shows how subsuming one to another hides the lack of representation of the subaltern in representation. In "*In the Penal Colony*", although the condemned man is politically represented by the Officer and re-presented by Kafka through this story, he never manages to be self-represented. He has an undefined existence and voice that are not heard.

Importantly, the disintegration of the execution machine in the latter part of the tale does not offer a solution to the subaltern condition. Although the death of the officer seems to signal justice, the structural pattern of oppression is still in place. Spivak cautions against assuming that the destruction of the individual operators of power leads to authentic liberation. Structural violence persists despite personal responsibility. The condemned man is unnamed, marginalized and silenced once more, buttressing the contention that subalternity is systemic rather than accidental. This conclusion directly addresses that the specific research gap rejects the simplistic reading of interpreting the resolution at the story's ending as a moral resolution.

Kafka's narrative, when viewed from a Spivakian perspective defies universalization and demands a more politicized reading. In placing the tale within a colonial construct and emphasizing epistemic violence, this analysis challenges mainstream critiquing discourses of Kafka that are more separate from colonial ideologies. Spivak personally had warned of such interpretations of her work, arguing that "to ignore the subaltern is to participate in their continued silencing" (Spivak, 1988). Kafka does not seek to offer 'subaltern' perspectives instead, he exposes how they are suppressed from being expressed. This strategy aligns with Spivak's ethical stance against ventriloquizing the subaltern's voice.

Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony* exemplifies the concept of consent without voice is expressed through the absolute silence enforced on the punished subject, in which his seeming subordination is conflated with consent. The condemned man does not utter any objection against his sentence, and his silence is not consent, it is produced by a system which deprives him of the very conditions required for him to utter anything. He is never made aware of the law he has broken and is not given the chance to prove himself innocent. Thus, Kafka illustrates the phenomenon of coerced consent in which consent is presumed only as the subject has been made voiceless.

The silence *In the penal colony* is institutionalized and enforced. In fact, this is incorporated in the very function of the execution machine as it substitutes words for inscriptions, where the law is etched on the body instead of being relayed orally. In this way, the punishment metes out justice without requiring any form of explanation or words, thus discarding the whole idea of using words. The presence of the Officer in the situation symbolizes words, while the accused is nothing but the object being punished. The whole process does away with words, thus presenting silence as a mandate instead of a choice. The lack of consent within the colony indicates the vastly unequal power relations that exist between the colonizer and the colonized. Power here rests with those in authority, people who are knowledgeable in the language of power, while the punished individual holds no power but only the body through which the power will be exercised. These vastly unequal power relations demonstrate that colonial justice becomes the translator that turns domination into legitimacy. The discussion highlights that a previous understanding of universality neglects this colonial specificity to subalternity. Finally, it is possible for this analysis to concur in the understanding that Kafka precedes Spivak in his description of the impossibility of subaltern discourse. This analysis now fulfills this evident and continuous research gap by providing a consistent Spivakian reading of the work entitled *In the Penal Colony*. Kafka's work

emerges through the concepts of subalternity, epistemic violence, and representation as a powerful critique of colonial justice and the structural silencing of marginal subjects. The failure of speech by the condemned man is not a narrative ellipsis but a theoretical statement that spoils Spivak's question, Can the subaltern speak? Kafka's response, like Spivak's, proves to be gruesomely unequivocal. Under conditions of colonial power, justice, and knowledge, the subaltern is denied those very conditions that make speech possible. It is acknowledged here that such awareness deepens our understanding of Kafka's work while repositioning it emphatically within postcolonial literary discourse.

Conclusion:

This study has posited that in Franz Kafka's *In the Penal Colony*, there exists a deeply disturbing depiction of consent minus voice through the careful subjugation of the punished subject under a colonial apparatus of law and justice. By employing a reading of Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's critical notion of subalternity, this paper has sought not merely to reinforce universal definitions of Kafka's abstract notion as a critic of bureaucracy/authoritarianism but has sought to realign the penal colony along more colonial lines as a space where the ideology of power/ knowledge/law intersect in order to negate the very notion of subaltern discourse. The subject's silence in the condemned man, far from being merely incidental or purely symbolic, occurs through the structural means of a system wherein compliance rests on a direct notion of consent. What emerges from this analysis is the fact that Kafka portrays in dramatic form what Spivak articulates as epistemic violence, namely the way in which colonial power makes subordinate discourses unintelligible in metropolitan legal and ethical discourses. The execution machine materializes epistemic violence with perfect objectivity, medicalizing law and turning it into a flesh inscription in the process. Justice in this understanding no longer demands explanation, dialogue, and justification; instead, it unfolds through pain, rituals, and repetitions of machines. Consent in this sense is presupposed, not as it has been given, but as it has been denied access to words and to power to deny it. Kafka's story brings to light the performative power of silence instead of its testimonial use as a sign of consent. Furthermore, the sociological exercise undertaken in this paper has drawn attention to the function of the mediating character in sustaining the silencing of the subaltern. While the fanatic dedication of the officer to the machine represents the internalization of the soul by the colonialist ideology, the Explorer's moment of moral reservation in the face of this situation embodies the position of the Western intellectual, in Spivak's definition, who watches the suffering of the world without challenging the structural causes of the pain. Neither the Officer nor the Explorer does anything to allow the speaking subject to be voiced. Representation in Spivak's terms again is necessarily distorted. The subaltern is spoken for, written upon, and interpreted, but never allowed self-representation. The rupture of the execution machine at the story's end offers no release from these ethical and political tensions. It speaks, if anything, to the continuity of structural violence beyond the collapse of its animated agents. In declining to provide catharsis or moral resolution, Kafka stresses the durability of structures that produce domination and silence. This can be related to Spivak's warning regarding the mistake of taking symbolic reversals as actual emancipation.

In the Penal Colony, therefore, through a Spivakian reading, presents itself as a very significant critique of the colonial form of justice and the phenomenon of consent in the presence of such vast disparities of power. Kafka has foreshadowed the ideas of the postcolonial movement by uncovering the way in which the law and the procedure of punishment conspire to silence the subaltern subjects and legitimize violence in the name of order and reason. In the light of the concept of consent without voice, the present study thus adds to Kafka's studies, thereby proving that Kafka has not only represented oppression but has actually theorized the impossibility of subaltern discourse in the colonial conditions. In such conditions, silence does not constitute the absence of voice but rather the product of the systematic destruction of the latter, which has been revealed in the works of Kafka as well as Spivak.

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